

Performance analysis of low Reynolds number vertical axis wind turbines using low-fidelity and mid-fidelity methods and wind conditions in the city of Nottingham

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ABSTRACT

The aerodynamics of small-scale Darrieus vertical axis wind turbines (VAWT) is investigated at chord-based Reynolds number between 1×10^5 and 1×10^6 . Initially, wind resource assessment is done for two locations in Nottingham, UK for 4 years. Both locations experience highly unsteady wind and the average wind speed is lower for the location within the city than outside the city. Next, two analytical aerodynamic methods are compared: low-fidelity Double Multiple Streamtube and mid-fidelity Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake methods. Five 3D design parameters are investigated: number of blades, blade shape, chord length, blade height and blade pitch angle. Overall, the power coefficient values and trends agree well between the two methods. The differences arise either in cases of very low solidity or high solidity. The unsteady flow field is visualized for each case using instantaneous vortices and streamwise velocity contours in the wake. The aim of the current work is twofold. Firstly, to investigate the difference between the two methods based on the physical principles modeled by each method. The second aim is to have a better understanding of the VAWT flow physics by studying the complex 3D force and flow field, and fluid dynamic interactions in the VAWT wake.

1. Introduction

The pursuit of sustainability in urban areas and the drive towards net-zero cities have spurred a growing interest in understanding the aerodynamics of small-scale vertical axis wind turbines operating at low Reynolds numbers. With projections indicating that 68% of the global population will reside in urban areas by 2050 (United Nations [1]), incorporating renewable energy sources into urban planning has become increasingly crucial. Moreover, as cities continue to evolve into thriving industrial centers, accommodating numerous small to medium-scale enterprises, the imperative to reduce carbon footprints intensifies. In this context, responsible sourcing of power becomes essential for companies aiming to align with sustainability goals. Urban wind turbines emerge as a viable solution, bridging the energy demand-supply gap in cities, especially when complemented by solar energy. These localized, off-grid systems not only minimize transmission losses [2–4], but also empower consumers to make conscious energy choices by transforming them into energy producers [5].

Urban areas are characterized by highly unsteady and turbulent wind conditions, with rapidly changing local wind directions [6–8]. This unique wind environment makes vertical-axis wind turbines

(VAWTs) a more suitable choice compared to horizontal-axis wind turbines (HAWTs) for urban applications [9]. VAWTs offer several advantages over HAWTs in urban settings, including lower cut-in wind speeds, reduced noise levels [10], superior self-starting capabilities, omnidirectional operation, and simplified ground-level maintenance requirements. Additionally, these characteristics make VAWTs well-suited for offshore installations, including floating wind turbines [11–13]. Notably, VAWT wind farms in urban areas have the potential to achieve significantly higher power generation per unit ground area compared to HAWT wind farms [14], making them an attractive option for maximizing the use of available land resources. In this study, we focus on investigating the performance of a lift-type VAWT, specifically the H-Darrieus turbine [15], within the context of urban wind power generation.

Darrieus VAWT consists of straight airfoil-shaped blades rotating vertically about an axis and generates tangential loading and torque using the lift produced by the blades. A schematic representation of Darrieus blades at different azimuthal locations and the velocities experienced are shown in Fig. 3(b). The turbine's performance is characterized by an optimal rotational speed for a given wind speed, which

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produces maximum power. Any change in rotational speed affects the performance negatively due to a decrease in velocity experienced by the blades, either due to lower rotational speed or a higher induction factor (in the case of higher rotational speed). Darrieus VAWT has high power generation potential [16–18] and therefore, fast adoption and public acceptance will be closely coupled to the improvement in VAWT technology over the next decade [19–22]. Moreover, the expertise gained in large wind turbine aerodynamics over the past decades cannot be directly utilized towards designing a small-scale wind turbine. This is due to the difference in aerodynamic phenomenon at Reynolds number ranging from 1×10^4 to 5×10^5 for the latter and the difference in fluid dynamic interactions arising due to the VAWT axis of rotation being perpendicular to the HAWT axis. The development of robust aerodynamic tools accurate for low Reynolds number applications and having lower computational costs is therefore essential. In addition, wind resource assessment for a location is essential to judge the feasibility of a wind turbine in both the short and long term.

Two common aerodynamic methods for VAWTs are low-fidelity Double Multiple Streamtube (DMS) and mid-fidelity Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake (LLFVW) which have been used in previous studies. Peng et al. [23] presented a systematic review of various methods for calculating VAWT performance and, near and far wake of VAWTs including the DMS method. Bangga et al. [24] presented the Improved-DMS (IDMS) method by introducing analytical corrections for blade angle of attack (AoA), streamtube expansion and dynamic stall effects. As an extension, Bangga et al. [25] presented a comparison between different approaches of various fidelities for calculating VAWT loads including DMS and Improved-DMS (IDMS) methods, and showed that low-fidelity methods produce a good agreement with vortex (mid-fidelity) and high-fidelity methods at low tip speed ratio (TSR). At high TSRs, discrepancies are reported due to wake expansion and highly unsteady interaction effects. Wu et al. [26] reported the effects of lateral gusts on VAWTs using the DMS method and the difference in AoA variation for upwind and downwind halves of rotation. Poguluri et al. [27] and Lee et al. [28] investigated co-axial contra-rotating VAWTs using both the DMS and high-fidelity CFD methods. Grasso et al. [29] presented a generalized lifting line code combined with the free vortex wake method for wind turbine aerodynamics. Extending this study further, Marten et al. [30] presented the application of the nonlinear LLFVW method to VAWT aerodynamics and Saverin et al. [31] performed experimental validation for wake features such as blade-tip vortices, dominant and submissive vortical structures, and periodic unsteadiness caused by the sectional dynamic stall.

The DMS method is a steady streamtube model while the LLFVW method is an unsteady free vortex wake model. The advantage of free wake convection is a much higher accuracy as the wake shape forms based on fundamental physical principles. Another advantage of vortex methods, as compared to streamtube and blade element methods, is the robust modeling of macroscopic flow physics. This reduces the requirement of empirical models (which are added in low-fidelity methods) related to microscopic fluid dynamics where boundary layer effects play an important role [32], such as dynamic stall, stall delay or tip loss corrections. Additionally, these methods provide simulation results for the unsteady velocity field around the rotor and wake for every time step, apart from overall rotor power and loading. On one hand, vortex wake methods are increasingly being used [33,34] and can be a potential replacement for blade element methods to achieve higher accuracy in VAWT design and certification applications. On the other hand, these vortex methods come at a significant computational cost and are, therefore, not suitable for early design stages and optimization (for which DMS is a better choice).

This study is divided into two parts. Firstly, local wind data is presented for an urban and a rural location in Nottingham, UK and the power production capacities of a few wind turbines are discussed. Nottingham is representative of any densely populated European city

and therefore this study can help to understand the behavior of an urban wind turbine when placed in any such city. Secondly, both DMS and LLFVW methods are used for the aerodynamic modeling of a range of VAWT configurations to explore the whole 3D design space. Open-source software QBlade CE 2.0.5.0 is used, to calculate the VAWT power performance and unsteady flow field. The results are validated with published mid-fidelity and high-fidelity CFD results [35]. The present study aims to compare and investigate the differences between the results of DMS and LLFVW methods for all VAWT configurations. This will help to quantify the accuracy of each method and relate the findings to the flow physics modeled by each.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reports the measured wind conditions in Nottingham, UK and the power production capacity of a few wind turbines. Section 3 presents the results obtained with the DMS and LLFVW methods. It starts with describing the methodology behind both the methods, wind turbine geometry and computational setup, numerical validation and convergence check, and, VAWT power performance and 3D flow field analysis for different TSRs and wind speeds for different design configurations. Finally, Section 4 discusses important conclusions for the study and recommendations for future work.

2. Power production estimation of wind turbines

2.1. Wind conditions in nottingham

The city of Nottingham is centrally located on the island of Great Britain and therefore, it experiences turbulent wind conditions coming from surrounding cities. This makes wind velocity and wind directions highly unsteady at any location within the city (and around) almost throughout the year. In the present study, Nottingham wind conditions were recorded using weather stations at two different locations named Watnall and Sutton Bonington, both at a height of 43 m. While Watnall is located northwest of Nottingham and falls within the bigger area of the city, Sutton is located in the southwest and is far away from any urban agglomeration. Fig. 1 shows the raw data of wind velocity recorded at the two locations, for a period of 4 years. The data shown are averaged over a period of every 1 h. The average wind speed for each location is also shown, in each figure.

Both locations exhibit highly unsteady wind conditions when observed over a yearly timeframe. Watnall experiences a lower average annual wind speed compared to Sutton. The presence of nearby structures in the vicinity of Watnall introduces greater turbulence and reduces wind velocity, which happens to a lesser degree in Sutton. Consequently, if an independent off-grid wind turbine is situated within an urban agglomeration, it will benefit from avoiding transmission losses but will encounter lower wind speeds in comparison to a rural setting.

For more comprehensive investigations of the wind conditions in the city of Nottingham, the reader is referred to another study by Shivangi et al. [36]. In this study, Watnall is selected as it offers more realistic data pertaining to urban wind turbines.

2.2. Small-scale wind turbines

The current study assumes that wind turbines are placed at exactly the same location as the weather station at Watnall. A total of five wind turbines are selected, shown in Table 1, the power curves of which are already available in the literature. Power predicted based on Watnall wind conditions is shown in Fig. 2.

The QR6 wind turbine demonstrates the highest power output, exhibiting a substantial difference from all other turbines. Notably, both helical designs outperform the remaining turbines, while the troposkien-shaped wind turbine exhibits the lowest power generation. Previous experience indicate two factors contributing to the observed power differences. Firstly, the size or swept area of the wind turbine is

Fig. 1. Wind conditions at the two locations in Nottingham. V_w represents instantaneous wind speed.

Fig. 2. Wind turbines selected in the current study.

Table 1
Wind turbines selected for power performance investigation in the city of Nottingham.

Wind turbine	Type	Diameter [m]	Height [m]
QR6 [39]	Darrieus - Helical	3.13	5.1
TURBY [40]	Darrieus - Helical	2	3
Battisti [41]	Darrieus - Straight	1.028	1.46
Battisti [41]	Darrieus - Troposkien	1.51	1.51
Doerffer [42]	Savonius - twin rotor	1.2	3.3

different for all designs considered, impacting the total oncoming wind power. QR6 is the biggest of all of them, in terms of swept area, and this allows for much higher power generation. Secondly, the aerodynamic design of the VAWT influences the fluid dynamic interactions between the blades and the wake. It is worth noting that the wind turbine's response to sudden wind fluctuations (gusts) is disregarded in this analysis, as the time interval of one hour is assumed sufficient for the turbine to average out such unsteady variations. The subsequent section investigates the complete 3D design space of a VAWT while maintaining a constant swept area, aiming to understand the impact of each design parameter and determine the most suitable choice for a city like Nottingham.

3. Performance analysis of VAWTs

3.1. Computational methodology

This study employs two distinct approaches to calculate the power coefficient of VAWTs. These methods include a low-fidelity Double Multiple Streamtube (DMS) method and a mid-fidelity unsteady Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake (LLFVW) method. The utilization of lower order models such as DMS and LLFVW offers notable advantages, including their straightforward simulation setup and comparatively lower computational requirements, even on standard personal computers. Despite their simplicity, these models provide a reasonably accurate

representation of the complex blade loading in VAWTs (in the case of DMS and LLFVW) and the unsteady flow field around the rotor (specifically in LLFVW).

3.1.1. Double Multiple Streamtube (DMS) method

This method is based on the model developed by Paraschivoiu [43] in 1988 and is derived from a combination of the actuator disk and the blade element theory [44,45], both of which are extensively used for a wind turbine or propeller low-fidelity aerodynamic analysis. The momentum conservation (from actuator disk theory) and forces on the blades (from blade element theory) are balanced until the system has reached convergence. In QBlade, an improved version of the model is used, called the Double Multiple Streamtubes Approach With Variable Interference Factors, originally proposed by Paraschivoiu [45].

The operation of a VAWT forms a bigger streamtube flowing through it, which is split into several smaller streamtubes, both in the cross-streamwise (lateral) and axial directions. VAWT blades, during its 360° circular path, pass through those streamtubes and extract energy from the flow, similar to the working of a horizontal axis wind turbine. Therefore, standard actuator disk theory can be applied to every small streamtubes mentioned above. In a single rotation, the blades pass through the streamtubes twice. To accommodate this, a single streamtube is divided into two parts: upstream and downstream halves, each having its own actuator disk. They act as two actuator disks working in tandem and mutually affect the fluid flowing through each of them [45]. The smaller streamtubes in the axial direction represent different blade sections at respective height, where they interact with the fluid flow. Each blade section is a 2D airfoil and is considered independent from other sections. The sections produce lift and drag forces based on the local angle of attack (α) which is calculated from the velocities experienced by each section. The resultant total forces on the blade are found by integrating over the whole blade length.

The interference factor indicates the amount of energy extracted by a single actuator disk and is calculated as a ratio of velocities downstream and upstream of the actuator disk. The two tandem actuator disks in the DMS method, therefore, have an upwind and a downwind interference factor. The iterative procedure is followed for the calculation of the interference factors at every blade height position for all upwind azimuthal angles (every small streamtube) until the user-defined convergence criteria are achieved. The convergence can be achieved separately for every azimuthal angle (when the interference factor is kept variable) or for the whole upwind rotor half (when the interference factor is kept constant).

Glauert's correction has been implemented with the most recent improvements based on experimental data [46], along with Lanchester-Prandtl model [47] for finite aspect ratio blades. Several dynamic stall models have been used (Berg, Strickland, and Paraschivoiu [45]) in addition to streamtube expansion models as mentioned by Paraschivoiu [45], to increase the accuracy of the aerodynamic calculations. The validation and prediction capabilities of the code used in this study

Fig. 3. VAWT setup (a) Geometry of 2-bladed Darrieus VAWT (b) Position of Darrieus blades over a single rotation, along with velocity diagram in the blade reference frame (adapted from Shubham et al. [37,38]) (c) Virtual camber airfoil geometry (green) and original airfoil geometry (red).

have been reported by Balduzzi et al. [35]. In the present study, all results with this method will henceforth be referred to with the ‘DMS’ nomenclature.

3.1.2. Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake (LLFVW) method

The lifting line method belongs to a family of various “vortex methods”, the computational cost of which falls somewhere in between low-fidelity momentum methods (BEMT, DMS, etc.) and high-fidelity CFD methods (Navier Stokes, Lattice-Boltzmann). In the present study, the lifting line theory coupled to a free vortex wake model is used to calculate the VAWT three-dimensional (3D) unsteady flow field past the rotor and the interaction between blade and fluid flow [35,48]. The LLFVW algorithm is based on nonlinear lifting line formulation by Garrel [49] and is mentioned in detail by Balduzzi et al. [35]. LLFVW method is used to compute the flow field in this study because it was shown to be accurate and efficient for similar low Reynolds number VAWT applications in another study by Shubham et al. [50].

The fluid is modeled as incompressible, inviscid and irrotational; the blade is modeled with a single line of vortices which is located on the quarter chord points of the blade. The wake is discretized into vortex line elements (straight or curved) and these elements are shed at the blade trailing edges at every time step. They then undergo free convection past the rotor (“free wake method”) in which the position of the wake end nodes is updated based on the local velocity, which is a combination of inflow velocity and induced velocity from all the wake elements in the domain. Nonlinear in the “nonlinear lifting line formulation” means the circulation calculated on the lifting line bound vortices is acquired from the nonlinear airfoil lift and drag data provided. Lift and drag forces are then calculated based on the local angle of attack (α).

The vortex elements are desingularized using the van Garrel’s cut-off method [32] with the vortex core size, taking into account viscous diffusion via the vortex core size that is modeled through the kinematic

viscosity ν , a turbulent vortex viscosity coefficient δ_v , and a time offset parameter S_c using the below equation:

$$r_c = \left(\frac{5.03\delta_v\nu(t + S_c)}{1 + \epsilon} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

The effects of unsteady aerodynamics and dynamic stall are introduced via the ATEFlap aerodynamic model [30,51] that reconstructs lift and drag hysteresis curves from a decomposition of the lift polars. The implemented ATEFlap formulation has been further adapted to work under the complex conditions of VAWT exhibiting large fluctuations in the angle of attack when rotating at low TSR [52]. Wake reduction schemes have been implemented to lower computational requirements [30,51–53]. In the present study, all results with this method will henceforth be referred to with the ‘LLFVW’ nomenclature.

3.2. Wind turbine geometry and airfoil data

A baseline geometry is selected from the previous work by Balduzzi et al. [35]. Darrieus H-rotor type VAWT is used consisting of straight blades with NACA 0021 symmetrical airfoil cross-section. The blade chord is 85.8 mm, blade length is 1.5 m and rotor diameter is 1.03 m. There is no central cylinder or supporting struts used. The geometry used in this study has been shown in Fig. 3(a), for a 2-bladed rotor.

Accurate and high-quality airfoil data is crucial to obtaining accurate results using low and mid-fidelity methods. From NACA 0021 profile, a virtual geometry is obtained to account for the virtual camber effect [54] using the conformal transformation technique based on the chord-to-radius ratio, as described by Bianchini et al. [55]. The transformed airfoil is shown in Fig. 3(c). Lift and drag polars are obtained for Reynolds number between 1×10^5 and 1×10^6 , using XFOil [56] with an $NCrit$ value of nine and forced transition at the leading edge of both the pressure and suction side. Airfoil static polar data is extrapolated to 360° angle of attack using the Montgomerie method [57] to ensure

Table 2
Simulation parameters used for DMS and LLFVW methods.

	DMS	LLFVW
Freestream velocity V_∞	9 m/s	9 m/s
Density	1.225 kg/m ³	1.225 kg/m ³
Kinematic viscosity	1.65 e-5 m ² /s	1.65 e-5 m ² /s
Blade discretization	21	21 (sinusoidal)
Azimuthal discretization	–	3 deg
Full wake length	–	12
Vortex time offset	–	1 e-4 s
Turbulent vortex viscosity	–	100

a smooth extrapolation in the post-stall regime. An example of 360° extrapolated polars is shown by Balduzzi et al. [35].

3.3. Computational setup and simulation campaign

Table 2 lists all the simulation parameters used in the present study. For validation, both the LLFVW and DMS results for the baseline geometry are compared with the results reported by Balduzzi [35] for the 1-bladed rotor.

A total of five simulation campaigns are conducted in the current study. Each campaign focuses on a particular design space parameter, the list of which is:

1. Number of blades
2. Blade shape
3. Chord length
4. Blade height
5. Blade pitch angle

A detailed analysis comprising all the above parameters aims to provide a thorough investigation into the 3D design space of a VAWT and a better understanding of the complex 3D force and flow field. For each VAWT configuration, a wide range of tip speed ratios (TSRs) are simulated. Tip speed ratio (TSR) is defined as the ratio of blade rotational speed and freestream velocity i.e. $\omega r/V_\infty$, where ω is the rotational speed in rad/s, r is the wind turbine radius in m and V_∞ is the freestream velocity in m/s. While V_∞ is kept constant at 9 m/s to match the reference value [35], the value of ω is varied to change the TSR value. This exercise is done to keep the investigation close to a practical case, where the control system varies rotational speed (ω) based on instantaneous wind speed measured, to keep the TSR at the optimal point. The variation in some of the above-listed parameters also leads to changes in non-dimensional quantities such as solidity (Nc/D) and rotor aspect ratio (s/D), where N is the number of blades, c is chord length, D is VAWT diameter and s is blade span. For variation in chord Reynolds number (Re_c) with TSR, a good overview is given by Pearson [58] who keeps the value constant at all TSRs. On that account, it is essential to point out for the present study, that the variation in some design space parameters leads to differences in Re_c (blade shape, chord length), whereas for others, Re_c stays the same (number of blades, blade height, pitch angle). Hence, the physical interpretation of results in the following few sections will incorporate this phenomenon too.

Table 3 lists this study's simulation campaigns and VAWT configurations. Power coefficient (C_p) and thrust coefficient (C_T) are calculated by non-dimensionalizing power and thrust values with the term $(1/2)\rho DsV_\infty^3$ and $(1/2)\rho DsV_\infty^2$, respectively, where ρ is the air density and V_∞ is freestream velocity. The non-dimensionalizing term represents the total wind power flowing into the wind turbine. Therefore, the swept area ($D \times s$) is kept the same for all VAWT geometries at 1.54 m² to ensure fairness in comparison. Fig. 4 shows a few geometries used in the simulation campaigns. It is to be noted that Troposkien-shape VAWT exhibits variable solidity due to the radius being different along the blade span; Table 3 lists the value only based

on equatorial diameter which is 1.55 m. Fig. 5 depicts a diagrammatic representation of the blade pitch angle; a negative pitch ($-\beta$) is shown in the right figure, also called toe-out configuration. Using DMS and LLFVW methods, simulations are performed with intervals of TSR = 0.1 and TSR = 1, respectively. On a workstation with 4 cores Intel 4 GHz processor, the total time taken by DMS and LLFVW simulations for all TSRs for each VAWT configuration is 1 min and 36 h, respectively.

3.4. Validation and sanity checks

Initial results obtained using both DMS and LLFVW methods are reported in this section. The QBlade setup in this study has already been used for a wide range of wind turbine aerodynamic studies, especially vertical axis wind turbines. Best practices have been followed to perform sensitivity analysis in regard to computational setup parameters such as the number of blade panels, azimuthal time step, length of wake and statistical time convergence. This is primarily done for the solver using the unsteady LLFVW method. Based on acquired experience and previous studies [59–61], these parameters are the main sources of numerical uncertainty and are vital to investigate before making a physical interpretation of results. Sensitivity analysis is generally performed for the most complex case, aerodynamically, but it is always helpful to investigate it for all cases.

A subset of results is reported for statistical time convergence of C_T and C_p for 1-bladed VAWT at TSR = 6 and 3-bladed VAWT at TSR = 5, shown in Fig. 6. For the former VAWT, convergence is clearly achieved after 8 rotor rotations, while for the latter VAWT, convergence is achieved after around 12 rotor rotations. This argument is supported by the low values of uncertainty u (percentage of standard deviation) reported, which is calculated after the 15th rotor rotation for mean values over a single rotation. These uncertainty values reflect the degree of uncertainty or variability in the computed thrust and power coefficients over time due to the inherent unsteadiness and randomness in the fluid dynamic interactions. A smaller value of u implies a higher level of confidence in the simulation outcomes, indicating that the simulation has achieved temporal convergence. Similar convergence behavior was found for all other VAWT configurations studied, the results of which are not shown to keep the paper concise. VAWTs operating at higher TSR experience higher blade-vortex interaction (BVI) and as a consequence, higher fluctuations in blade loading and a delayed time convergence, than at lower TSR [62]. Therefore, time convergence for TSR = 5 and 6 guarantees the same for all lower TSR values. This phenomenon can also be understood by comparing the 1-bladed and 3-bladed VAWT results in Fig. 6, the latter of which has more BVI [9,37,63]. Following the best practice, all results reported henceforth are extracted after 20th rotor rotation for the unsteady LLFVW method.

Fig. 7 compares C_p values for a 1-bladed VAWT (of Campaign 1) with the results reported by Balduzzi et al. [35]. The reference dataset consists of the mid-fidelity LLFVW method and the high-fidelity 3D CFD method (only for TSR = 3.3) utilizing the compressible formulation of the Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations. On the whole, both the DMS and LLFVW methods used in this study predict the typical shape of the VAWT power curve [45,58] in a satisfactory way. LLFVW results match very well with reference results, over the whole range of TSR, except for a slight mismatch around TSR = 2. DMS method predicts well at high TSRs (5 to 8), where blades experience low angle of attack and high BVI, and predicts lower values at low TSRs (1 to 5), where blades experience high angle of attack and dynamic stall. DMS method predicts lower optimal power values as compared to LLFVW, while the TSR for optimal power around 4.3 to 4.4 and zero-power condition around TSR = 7.5 is very well predicted by all methods. These arguments point out that the DMS method can be relied upon for high TSR cases, but needs to be dealt with carefully for low TSR cases. Although this can be concluded only for 1-bladed VAWT for now, the next few sections will make the distinction between the two methods clearer for other turbine configurations.

Table 3
List of simulation campaigns in the current study. Bold numbers/letters represent the design parameter in focus in a particular campaign; SB – Straight-bladed, TB – Troposkien-bladed.

	Number of blades	Chord length	Diameter	Blade height	Pitch angle	Solidity	Blade shape
Campaign 1	1	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.08	SB
	2	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.16	SB
	3	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.24	SB
	4	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.32	SB
Campaign 2	3	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.24	SB
	3	0.086 m	1.55 m	1.5 m	0°	0.17	TB
Campaign 3	2	0.043 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.08	SB
	2	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.16	SB
	2	0.129 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.24	SB
Campaign 4	2	0.086 m	3.08 m	0.5 m	0°	0.055	SB
	2	0.086 m	1.54 m	1.0 m	0°	0.11	SB
	2	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.16	SB
Campaign 5	3	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	0°	0.24	SB
	3	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	-2°	0.24	SB
	3	0.086 m	1.03 m	1.5 m	2°	0.24	SB

Fig. 4. A few geometries used in the current study.

Fig. 5. Preset blade pitch on a VAWT blade. A negative pitch (toe-out) configuration with angle $-\beta$ is shown on the right.

3.5. Rotor power performance and flowfield analysis

Figs. 8 and 9 show the comparison of power coefficient (C_p) values predicted by both DMS and LLFVW methods, for all simulation campaigns. The left figures are for DMS while the right ones are for LLFVW. The following discussions will comprise two portions: power

prediction capability for low-Reynolds number VAWT using LLFVW and DMS methods, and giving the reader a physical insight into the effect of 3D design parameters on power performance. It is also interesting to compare qualitative results using the LLFVW method to visualize the unsteady flowfield for each test case. Figs. 10 and 11 depict instantaneous vortices in the downstream part of VAWT flowfield using

Fig. 6. Statistical variation of thrust and power coefficient with time (number of rotations) for two different VAWT configurations; uncertainty u denotes the level of stationarity achieved after 15th rotation.

Fig. 7. Comparison of C_p values for a 1-bladed VAWT with the results reported by Balduzzi et al. [35]; both the streamtube (DMS) and vortex methods (LLFVW) have been reported from the present study.

a system of the shed and trailing vortices, while Figs. 12 and 13 portray instantaneous streamwise velocity contours in the VAWT wake on a 2D plane situated at the blade mid-span location.

Comparison between DMS and LLFVW methods: Overall, the datasets shown illustrate a fairly good agreement between the values and trends predicted by both methods. This is true for the whole range of TSRs investigated. More in detail: for lower TSRs, DMS predicts slightly lower values when compared to the LLFVW method. The difference between them increases for high-solidity cases, as seen in Fig. 8(a) and (b) with a higher number of blades and in (e) and (f) with a longer chord. In the case of higher TSRs, DMS predicts close to LLFVW for low-solidity configurations and predicts higher values for high-solidity configurations; this is also true for optimal power values.

Configurations with less solidity have a smaller velocity induction factor and less blade-vortex interaction (BVI) than the configurations with high solidity. Similarly, the induction factor and BVI also increase with TSR. Based on the above observations, it can be argued that both

methods differ when either or both of the above-mentioned phenomena play an important role. The induction factor affects the velocities induced at the blades and normal and tangential loading as a result. At low TSRs, the induction factor predicted by LLFVW is lower for high solidity cases, and therefore velocities and tangential loading is higher, than DMS. At high TSRs, the opposite trend can be attributed to the effect of BVI. LLFVW being a vortex method captures the effect of BVI in a fairly accurate manner when compared to the DMS method, which is a streamtube model. C_p predicted by LLFVW is lower than DMS in such high TSR and solidity cases since interaction with wake vortices disturbs the ideal pressure distribution on VAWT blades and negatively affects tangential loading.

The simulation campaign for different blade heights offers additional insight into the above argument. When blade height reduces, rotor diameter is increased to keep a constant swept area; this decreases rotor solidity to very low values (0.055 and 0.11). At low TSRs, DMS still predicts lower values than LLFVW. But at optimal and high TSR values, DMS predicts lower values than LLFVW by a large margin for very low-solidity cases. Based on this observation, the previous argument can be expanded further: both for low and high TSRs, LLFVW predicts lower induction factors and high induced velocities at the blades, as compared to DMS. The differences get bigger as solidity decreases (or diameter increases). If we move towards higher solidity designs, BVI increases and LLFVW power values decrease to less than DMS values; this is especially true for high TSR conditions.

Physics of 3D design space: At low TSRs, having higher solidity helps to achieve more power. This is seen in the results of simulation campaigns for the variation in the number of blades, chord length and blade height (with change in diameter). The same campaigns show the opposite trend at high TSRs: higher solidity gives lower C_p values. Blades act more independently at low TSR and increasing solidity negligibly increases blade-wake/blade-vortex interaction; this helps increase total blade tangential loading and power produced. As TSR increases, induction factor and blade-wake/blade-vortex interaction also increase and increasing solidity worsens the tangential loading on each blade

Fig. 8. Power coefficient variation with TSR for different simulation campaigns.

and the overall rotor power. Consequently, higher solidity leads to a sharper gradient in C_p values than lower solidity cases, over the whole range of TSR. These observations also show that VAWT design optimization with an objective to increase its self-starting capability (C_p at very low TSR) will therefore lean towards higher solidity designs.

The above discussion can be qualitatively visualized from Figs. 10 and 11. A train of trailing and shed vortices can be seen, obtained from the LLFVW method. Both for the higher solidity and higher TSR, wake vortex structures are denser and closer for every subsequent

blade rotation. For lower solidity and lower TSR, wake vortices convect downstream in a more organized manner and are equally spaced. Furthermore, Figs. 12 and 13 also show that higher solidity and higher TSR exhibit stronger wake, which is illustrated by lower streamwise velocity in the downstream direction. This is a consequence of higher induction factors and affects the VAWT blade loading as explained above. The uniform train of wake vortices can also be clearly seen in lower solidity and lower TSR cases and starts to vanish as one or both parameters increase. Another important observation, in all the cases,

Fig. 9. Power coefficient variation with TSR and three different pitch angles.

Fig. 10. Instantaneous vortices visualization in the VAWT wake using the Q-criterion for different simulation campaigns using mid-fidelity LLFVW method; a system of the shed and trailing (tip) vortices can be seen.

Fig. 11. Instantaneous vortices visualization in the VAWT wake using the Q-criterion for different simulation campaigns using mid-fidelity LLFVW method; a system of the shed and trailing (tip) vortices can be seen.

is the non-symmetrical nature of wake in the lateral/cross-streamwise direction. This is a characteristic behavior of VAWT wake and has been previously investigated through various methods [11].

Fig. 8(c) and (d) show that straight-bladed VAWT design produces more power at low TSRs than troposkien-bladed VAWT, and vice-versa. It is important to point out that for the same TSR, rotational speed of the former is higher than the latter. Eg. for TSR = 3, RPM for the former is 500.64 and for the latter is 332.74. This is done to have a fair comparison between the two designs since the rotor radius decreases

from equator to pole for the troposkien VAWT blades. A few authors have kept the same RPM in previous studies though [41]. Self-starting capability at low TSR is better with straight blades since a smaller radius of troposkien blades near the poles results in lower tangential loading. At high TSR, negligible tip vortices for troposkien blades play a key role in maintaining better performance than straight blades. This can be observed from Fig. 10(e) and (f) which show no clear trailing vortex line from the troposkien blade tip, as is generally seen with straight blades. Similar to the latter, the former shows organized and

Fig. 12. Instantaneous streamwise velocity (V_y) visualization in the VAWT wake for different simulation campaigns; dotted circle represents the path taken by the VAWT blade.

spaced vortices at low TSR, whereas high TSR displays more dense and unorganized vortex lines signaling high BVI. At TSR = 4, straight blades (Fig. 10(d)) exhibit stronger BVI than troposkien blades (Fig. 10(f)), which is the reason for the results observed. These arguments are also supported by streamwise velocity contour plots in Fig. 12(e) and (f). A hybrid design will be investigated in the future that will aim to have a balanced performance between the two designs.

The advantage of having a toe-out (negative pitch angle) configuration can be seen in Fig. 9. There is a negligible difference in power at low TSRs (confirmed by both DMS and LLFVW), while power increases at the optimal TSR and higher TSRs. The pitch angle variation leads to a change in angle of attack (AoA) experienced by the blades: toe-out shifts the whole AoA curve (across 360° azimuthal angle) upward by

the same value of pitch angle, while toe-in shifts the curve downward. The former increases AoA and improves tangential loading in the upwind part of rotation, but it does have a slight nullifying effect through a decrease in AoA in the downwind part; overall, tangential loading improves for the rotor. The opposite story happens for the latter configuration. As is more noticeable from LLFVW results, C_p vs TSR gradient for toe-out configuration is more than other configurations; similar behavior is seen with all other design parameters. Higher the blade loading, higher the increase in induction factor for the overall rotor as TSR increases. At high TSRs, the rate of decrease in induced velocity and tangential loading for the blades is, therefore, higher. Another consequence of higher blade loading is stronger wake and vortices, which is more evident when Fig. 11(e) is compared with (f) and slightly evident when Fig. 13(c) is compared with (d).

Fig. 13. Instantaneous streamwise velocity (V_y) visualization in the VAWT wake for different simulation campaigns; dotted circle represents the path taken by the VAWT blade.

3.6. Wind turbine power output

Fig. 14 shows the variation in C_p with wind speeds, for a wide range of VAWT configurations obtained using the DMS method. The objective is to get a better understanding of the choice of design parameters based on local wind speeds in an urban or offshore setting. The DMS method becomes valuable for such analysis due to the extremely less computational cost to simulate a range of TSR for given wind speeds. The maximum RPM of all wind turbines is limited to 450 (a usual limit for full-scale VAWT) and C_p values are calculated such that optimal TSR (maximum power achievable) is maintained at all wind speeds. The cut-in and cut-out wind speeds are 1 m/s and 10 m/s. Results are shown for the range 2–10 m/s since 1 m/s is too less to observe a difference between different configurations and above 10 m/s is generally unusual for a VAWT to experience.

On the whole, all turbines produce comparable power at lower wind speeds while a higher solidity turbine favors better at higher wind speeds. This is seen in Fig. 14(a) and (c). To be specific, the 3-bladed turbine produces slightly more power than 2, 4 and 1-bladed turbines at low wind speeds, although the difference between the former three turbines is negligible. Fig. 8(a) showed that at optimal TSR, C_p of the 3-bladed turbine is slightly higher than 2 and 4-bladed turbines and much higher than 1-bladed turbine and this reflects in the power output at lower wind speeds. At higher wind speeds, TSR decreases to less than optimal TSR value due to the constraint applied to maximum RPM and higher solidity turbines are a better choice then. Similar arguments can be made for variation in chord length which leads to changes in rotor solidity. The story of variation in blade height (with variation in rotor diameter) is opposite to the above two observations. The highest solidity turbine ($h = 1.5$ m) performs best at low wind speeds, whereas at higher wind speeds above 8.1 m/s, the turbine with $h = 1.0$ m (solidity in between the two extremes) performs the best. The reason is an added variation in rotor diameter: at 10 m/s, the maximum C_p achievable by $h = 1.5$ m turbine is 0.117 at TSR = 2.43 and by $h = 1$ m turbine is 0.234 at TSR = 3.63.

The straight-bladed turbine produces more power at lower wind speeds while the troposkien shape is a better option for higher wind speeds. At lower wind speeds, the maximum C_p achievable for VAWT

with straight blades is higher than with troposkien blades. Only at higher wind speeds above 8.6 m/s, the maximum TSR achievable with straight blades decreases such that C_p values become less than with troposkien blades. Eg. at 10 m/s, the maximum C_p achievable for the former is 0.19 at TSR = 2.43 and for the latter is 0.31 at TSR = 3.65. Finally, VAWT with toe-out configuration (pitch = -2°) produces the highest power at lower wind speeds and does so up until 8.5 m/s, after which zero pitch angle is a better choice. The toe-in (pitch = 2°) configuration comes out to be the worst choice at all wind speeds. This is related to the pitch angle dataset shown in Fig. 9, similar to the variation with number of blades and chord length.

From Section 2.1, the average wind speed in Watnall, Nottingham is 2.57 m/s, which represents a typical value for dense urban areas. According to the above observations, a suitable wind turbine for Nottingham should have straight-shaped 2 or 3 blades, a balance between high and low solidity with respect to chord size, a large aspect ratio and a small toe-out pitch configuration.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

The study focuses on the power performance of small-scale vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) operating at low Reynolds number. The objective of the study is twofold. Firstly, to perform a wind resource assessment of locations within and around an urban area (Nottingham, UK). Secondly, to perform an aerodynamic investigation of VAWTs by exploring the 3D design space of the rotor and the effect on power output with variation in tip speed ratio (TSR) and wind speed. Two methods are used: low-fidelity Double Multiple Streamtube (DMS) and mid-fidelity Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake (LLFVW) methods. The former is based on actuator disk and blade element methods while the latter is a vortex method. The objective is to compare the VAWT power predictions using both methods and develop an understanding of the physics modeled by each method and its effect on power performance. This will help to make an informed choice about such analytical methods for different applications.

Wind data is shown for two locations in Nottingham, UK. One of them is within the city limits and another one is far away from any urban agglomeration. Both locations experience highly unsteady wind conditions, observed over a period of 4 years. The average wind speed

Fig. 14. Power coefficient variation with wind speed for all simulation campaigns, calculated using DMS method.

within the city is 2.57 m/s and outside is 3.33 m/s. Five wind turbines are compared by predicting power production based on Nottingham wind conditions. A large variation in power is seen between such wind turbines.

Next, a total of five design parameters are investigated: number of blades, blade shape, chord length, blade height and blade pitch angle. The results of power coefficient (C_p) variation with TSR for different VAWT design configurations are compared between the two methods, DMS and LLFVW. As a whole, the two methods have similar C_p values and trends for the whole TSR range, with differences arising for specific cases. For low TSRs (1-3) and high TSRs (4-6), LLFVW is found to predict higher values and lower values for C_p as compared to DMS, respectively. This is true for all design parameters. In the case when solidity is slightly low (0.08 for 1-bladed VAWT), the match between the two methods is very good at high TSRs. When solidity drops even further (0.055 for blade height of 0.5 m and diameter of 3.08 m), LLFVW predicts higher values than DMS for all of the TSR range. A similar story is for the maximum C_p value for optimal TSR: the match is better when solidity is less although LLFVW predicts lower values than DMS when solidity increases. These observations show that DMS predicts higher values of induction factors and lower values of induced velocities at the blades, as compared to LLFVW. As solidity slightly increases, the results come closer. When solidity is high, at high TSRs,

the trend between DMS and LLFVW is reversed. This also shows the effect of BVI in LLFVW, which captures the unsteady phenomenon in a more accurate manner and is the reason for lower C_p values at high TSRs.

VAWTs have a large 3D design space and are characterized by complex 3D force and flow field. The development of VAWT technology will depend significantly on the maturity of modeling techniques, which can model physical phenomena in an accurate manner and still have lower computational expenses. This study provides a step towards that direction by comparing the two most common analytical methods. Low-fidelity methods can be a good replacement for mid-fidelity methods, but only in cases when the fluid dynamic interactions are limited. This can allow for faster VAWT design and optimization. In other cases, mid-fidelity vortex methods seem to be a better choice. New methods must be explored, such as Actuator Cylinder (AC) model, Vortex Panel Method (VPM), Non-linear Vortex Lattice Method (NVLM) and Reformulated Vortex Particle Method (RVPM). These studies should be validated with high-fidelity studies, using Navier–Stokes (NS) solver or Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM), and experiments. In future publications, results will be shown for an open-air experiment currently being conducted on the Clifton campus of Nottingham Trent University, UK, using a helical-bladed Darrieus VAWT. These results will be compared with high-fidelity LBM results.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Shubham Shubham: Conceptualization, Software, Setup, Validation, Analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Kevin Naik:** Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Shivangi Sachar:** Conceptualization, Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Anton Ianakiev:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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